

ANCIENT TOPONYMS IN THE WORKS OF ABU RAYKHAN BERUNI

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the life, scientific activity of Abu Raykhan Beruni, as well as the formation of the toponymic history of Central Asian cities and their naming in his works.

Keywords: encyclopedist, work, analysis, toponomics, territory, city, science, activity, river, history, scientific, natural sciences.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada Abu Rayhon Beruniyning hayoti, ilmiy faoliyati hamda uning asarlarida O'rtta Osiyo shaxarlarining toponimik tarixining shakllanishi va ularning nomlanishi haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: qomusiy olim, asar, tahlil, toponomika, hudud, shahar, fan, faoliyat, daryo, tarix, ilmiy, tabiiy fanlar.

Аннотация: В статье дается подробная информация о жизни и научной деятельности Абу Райхана Беруни, а также о формировании топонимической истории городов Средней Азии и их наименовании в его трудах.

Ключевые слова: энциклопедист, труд, анализ, топономика, территория, город, наука, деятельность, река, история, научный, естественные науки.

One of the encyclopedists, Abu Raykhan al-Biruni, was one of the great encyclopedists of the Middle Ages. His greatness is reflected in the unique scientific heritage he contributed to almost all sciences of that era.

He was engaged not only in astronomy and other natural sciences, but also in history and the history of religion. With more than 160 works written by the scientist, he made a huge contribution to the development of astronomy, astrology, mathematics, geography, geodesy, geology, mineralogy, arithmetic, medicine, history, philology and other sciences.[1]

In addition to his native Khorezm language, Beruni knew Persian, Arabic, Greek, Hebrew and Syriac, and at the age of 50 he learned Sanskrit. Abu Raykhan Beruni provided information about the cities of Central Asia and Khorasan in his works. He wrote works such as "Monuments of Ancient Peoples", "Geodesy", "Masud's Law", "Mineralogy", "Pharmacognosy", "Kitab at-Tafkhim", "Understanding Astrology", "History of Khorezm". [2]

Almost all of his works mention the cities of Central Asia, describing either their history, climate or population. Beruni mentioned more than 400 villages, mountains, rivers, cities and islands in his work "Saydana", and more than 600

place names in his book “Masud’s Law”. Of these, 85 belong to Central Asia and Khurosan. The book “Masud’s Law” shows the longitudes and latitudes of these places and gives a brief explanation of almost all of them. Balkh - the ancient name is Bomi. Obiskur - on the (Caspian) sea, the port of the city of Jurjan, in the Jurjan province. On the Kalif-Jaykhun river, in the Khurosan province. Maymana - now Jahudon, in the Khorasan province.

Wakhan - on the border of the ruby deposits, in the Khorasan province. Bolkhan - here the Jaykhun river turns and flows into the Jurjan sea, in the Ghuzia province. Jurjaniya - one of the cities of Khurosan, west of Jaykhun. [3] Kot - the second city (of Khorasan), on the eastern bank of Jaykhun, in the Khorasan province. Omuyya - the place where (Khorasan) crosses to Movuraunnakhr, in the Khorasan province. Tawvis - a place where there is an annual market. In the Khorasan province. Barskhan - next to Issyk-Kul, this is a hot lake.

In the Turkestan region, Abu Raykhan Beruni in his work “Masud’s Law” listed the cities of Central Asia in a table format and gave toponymic information about them. In particular, Tashkent is mentioned as follows: “Binkat is one of the cities of Shash, in Turkish Tashkent. This is the Burj al-Hijra fortress of Greek authors”.

In addition, the following territories are also named differently in the work: Baykand (Poykand) - a city located southwest of Bukhara. Ruins near the current Yakkatut station. It was also called Badzarubai. Kesh (Kitab and Shahrisabz) - called Majam at in Persian. Sutkent - a city on the Khasart River. Karyat al-Hadisa - near the confluence of the Khasart River, near Lake Khorezm, Guzlar region. Yangikent - in the foothills of the Syrdarya River (opposite the current city of Kazalinsk, ruins on the left side of the river). Yangikent - Janikent in Turks, “Kariyat al-Hadisa” in Arabs (qariyat - village, khodiza - new, i.e. “new village”) and “Madinat al-Jadida” (madina - city. jadida - New city) and Tajiks wrote Dekhinav (dekh - village, nav - new, New village). In addition, the scientist also cited the names of rivers in his works. One of them is Syrdarya. Syrdarya - Hasart. In his works in Greek, it is given as Yaksart. [4] But this is not the Greek name of Syrdarya, but the name Hasart (or Kasart) was corrupted in Greek and took the form of Yaksart. 120 years ago, the Polish orientalist I. Lelewellyn managed to compile a map of Central Asia based on the Beruniy table. He wrote the names of 40 cities and rivers and 8 regions on his map.

Abu Raykhan Beruni’s geographical and toponymic heritage is presented in the works “History of India”, “Al-Osarul Bakiya”, “Masud’s Law”. The scientist

said that among the Khorezmians, Vakhsh was the name of a goddess who controlled the waters, including the Jaykhun River. [5] Therefore, toponyms such as Vakhsh, a right tributary of the Amu Darya, and Vakhshivardara in the Surkhandarya region, are a reflection of the name of that mermaid. In the work "Geodesy", Beruni called the Sarikamisli commune of that time Khiz Tengiz, that is, "Maiden Sea". The scientist expressed a number of opinions regarding the laws of toponymy, for example, he says that the meaning of a number of words changed as a result of the Greeks and Arabs distorting and pronouncing Turkic words to suit their own languages.

In conclusion, it should be said that Abu Raykhan Beruni, in his works, fully described and analyzed the toponymic names of cities, regions, and rivers in Central Asia.

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